

A Prospective Observational Study On Comparing The Efficacy Of Acamprosate And Baclofen In The Treatment Of Alcohol Use Disorder In A Tertiary Care Hospital

R.V.S.S. Latha Sri^{2*}, A. Chandra Sekhar¹, R. Srinivas¹, S. Divya¹, T. Vamsi¹, J.N. Suresh Kumar³

¹Department of Pharmacy Practice, Narasaraopet Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Narasaraopet, Palnadu (Dist.).

²Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmacy Practice, Narasaraopet Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Narasaraopet, Palnadu (Dist.).

³Principal, Department of pharmaceuticals, Narasaraopet Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Narasaraopet, Palnadu (Dist.).

ABSTRACT

Title: A Prospective Observational Study on Comparing the Efficacy of Acamprosate and Baclofen in the Treatment of Alcohol Use Disorder in a Tertiary Care Hospital. **Background:** Alcohol Use Disorder (AUD) is a chronic and relapsing condition characterized by an inability to control alcohol consumption despite its harmful consequences. Pharmacological interventions such as Acamprosate and Baclofen are commonly used to reduce alcohol cravings and prevent relapse. However, comparative studies evaluating their efficacy remain limited. This study aims to compare the effectiveness of Acamprosate and Baclofen in managing AUD symptoms and reducing cravings. **Methods:** A prospective observational study was conducted over six months at a tertiary care hospital. A total of 120 male patients aged 20-75 years, diagnosed with AUD based on DSM-5 criteria, were enrolled. Patients were equally divided into two groups, receiving either Acamprosate (666 mg TID) or Baclofen (10–20 mg TID). The primary outcome was measured using the Penn Alcohol Craving Scale (PACS) at baseline, 30 days, and 60 days. The Severity of Alcohol Dependence Questionnaire (SAD-Q) was also used to assess the degree of dependence. Additional sociodemographic parameters, including marital status, education, and occupation, were analyzed to determine their association with AUD. **Results:** Both treatment groups showed significant reductions in craving scores over 60 days. The PACS scores indicated a greater reduction in alcohol cravings among Baclofen users compared to Acamprosate users (10.65 vs. 11.47 at 60 days). Middle-aged individuals (35–49 years) exhibited the highest incidence of AUD, with daily wage workers and drivers being the most affected occupational groups. Sociodemographic factors such as marital status and education level were found to influence AUD prevalence. **Conclusion:** Both Acamprosate and Baclofen were effective in managing AUD by reducing cravings and preventing relapse. Baclofen demonstrated a slightly superior reduction in craving levels, suggesting it may be more beneficial in the early stages of treatment. These findings highlight the importance of individualized treatment strategies for AUD patients. Future studies should focus on long-term efficacy, relapse prevention, and the impact of these medications in diverse patient populations.

Keywords: Aloe vera, diabetes management, cancer therapy, skincare, bioactive compounds, pharmacological potential, natural remedies.

INTRODUCTION

Alcohol, chemically ethanol, is the psychoactive component of beverages like beer, wine, and distilled

spirits. It is manufactured through the fermentation of sugars. Alcohol, primarily composed of ethanol, is a psychoactive substance commonly found in beverages like beer, wine, and distilled spirits. It is

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

produced through the fermentation of sugars derived from various organic sources. While alcohol consumption is widespread across different cultures, excessive and prolonged use can lead to Alcohol Use Disorder (AUD)—a chronic, relapsing brain condition characterized by compulsive drinking, an inability to regulate alcohol intake, and distressing emotional states during periods of abstinence. AUD has profound physical, psychological, and social repercussions. Chronic alcohol consumption can result in severe health issues, including liver cirrhosis, cardiovascular diseases, neurological impairments, and a weakened immune system. Additionally, it significantly increases the risk of mental health disorders such as depression and anxiety. On a social level, AUD often leads to strained relationships, occupational instability, legal troubles, and social isolation. The development of AUD is influenced by multiple factors, including genetic predisposition, early exposure to alcohol, co-existing mental health conditions, and environmental influences. While behavioural therapies and support groups play a crucial role in treatment, pharmacological interventions are often essential to help individuals manage cravings and reduce the risk of relapse. According to the National Family Health Survey-5 (NFHS-V), 11.5% of the population in Andhra Pradesh consumes alcohol, which is slightly higher than the national average of 9.9%. However, alcohol consumption in Andhra Pradesh is lower than many of its neighbouring states like Arunachal Pradesh (77%), Goa (59%), Telangana (50%).

Given the complexity and chronic nature of AUD, treatment requires a comprehensive approach that includes behavioural therapies, support groups, and pharmacological interventions. Behavioural therapies such as Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (CBT) and Motivational Enhancement Therapy (MET) have been shown to be effective in helping individuals modify drinking behaviours and develop healthier coping strategies. However, medication-assisted treatment (MAT) is often necessary to manage cravings and prevent relapse. Among the pharmacological options, **Acamprosate and Baclofen** are two commonly used anti-craving agents for AUD. Acamprosate helps restore the balance between excitatory and inhibitory neurotransmitters in the brain, reducing cravings and withdrawal

symptoms. It is excreted primarily by the kidneys and is considered safe for individuals with liver disease. Baclofen is a GABA-B receptor agonist that reduces alcohol cravings and withdrawal symptoms. It has shown efficacy in patients with liver cirrhosis, making it a viable option for those with alcohol-related liver damage.

By conducting a prospective observational study, this research aims to provide insights into the efficacy of these medications in real-world clinical settings. The findings will contribute to the development of improved treatment protocols, ensuring that patients receive the most suitable therapy based on their individual needs.

MATERIALS & METHODS

Study design: A hospital based prospective study aimed to compare the efficacy of acamprosate and baclofen in the treatment of alcohol used disorder in a tertiary care hospital. A prospective observational study design was chosen to comparing the efficacy of baclofen and acamprosate.

Study period: This study was conducted for a period of 6 months.

Period of data collection: 6 months – the patients who received the treatment between the periods August 2024 to January 2025.

Study site: This study was conducted at the Department of Psychiatry, Area Hospital, Narasaraopet. The data was collected from the outpatients and inpatients for this project.

Sample size: The collected sample size is 120.

Data source: The study utilized medical records from outpatients/inpatients medical records for a period spanning. These records included detailed information on patient demographics, medical history, treatment regimens, laboratory results, and follow up visits and documented.

Inclusion criteria: Patients who are between 20 -75 years of age were considered, Patients who are Diagnosed with AUD by DSM-5 criteria were included in this study, Only male patients were

included, Patients with abnormal and normal liver function tests were included.

Exclusion criteria: Patients who have shorter/incomplete follow-up were excluded, Patients with presence of another current co-existing major psychiatric disorder were not considered in the study, Patients with history of hypersensitivity reactions with these drugs in the past were excluded, Patients who are not willing to participate was excluded.

Exposure: The primary exposure of interest was the use of either baclofen or Acamprosate for the treatment of alcohol use disorder

Study procedure: The Severity of Alcohol Dependence Questionnaire (SAD-Q) scale was applied to assess and quantify the severity of alcohol dependence. This is a 20-item clinical tool is classified as mild dependence (score 8-15), moderate dependence (score 16-30), and severe dependence (score 31- 60). The Penn Alcohol Craving Scale (PACS) was used to quantify craving for alcohol during follow-up. It is a self-report measure with five items that includes questions related to frequency, intensity, and duration of craving, the ability to resist drinking, and an overall rating of craving for alcohol in the previous week. Each item is scored from 0 to 6, and the maximum total score can be 30. Medical management of alcohol withdrawal in these patients was done using lorazepam 2mg or Diazepam 10mg, which was tapered over five days along with co-administration of 300-500 mg of thiamine per day. In addition, Cognitive behavioral therapy was given to

the patient. After the management of acute symptoms of alcohol withdrawal over five days, liver function tests (LFT) were done to the patients. Based on the liver function tests, subjects with normal LFT's are prescribed with Acamprosate. The dosage of acamprosate was 1,998 mg/day (if weight \geq 60 kg) and 1,332 mg/day (if weight < 60 kg). Subjects with abnormal LFT's are prescribed with baclofen 20- 30 mg/day in divided doses. Anti-craving effects of these agents were compared using the PACS score between the 0th Day (initial), 30th Day, 60th Day between two treatment groups for 2 months of period.

This study was a dissertation project and was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee of Narsaropeta institute of pharmaceutical sciences, Narasaropet, Andhra Pradesh, Letter no. IEC/2024/06.

RESULTS

In our study all the study participants were males, 120 patients have included in the study were 60 patients treated with Acamprosate and 60 patients treated with Baclofen in 1:1 ratio are taken. 17% of middle-aged individuals (35-49 years) exhibited the highest incidence of AUD followed by 45-49 age group with 15%, in occupational group daily wage workers (26%) and drivers (22%) being the most affected. Sociodemographic factors such as marital status and education level were found to influence AUD prevalence where 80% patients are illiterates, 90% are married.

Severity	No. of Patients (N=120)	Percentage (%)
Mild	3	2.5
Moderate	58	48.3
Severe	59	49.2

Table 1: Severity of alcohol dependence in the study sample.

Using the SAD-Q scale, Out of 120 patients 58 patients (48.3%) were under moderate alcohol dependence, while 59 patients (49.2%) were under severe alcohol dependence. Only a small fraction i.e, 3 patients (2.5%) exhibited mild alcohol dependence (Table 1).

Table 2: shows a significant reduction in craving severity who are taking Acamprosate by using PACS score. On the 0th day, most patients (40) experienced severe cravings, while 10 had moderate cravings, and none reported mild cravings. By the 30th day, severe cravings drastically decreased to 3, with moderate cravings increasing to 47, and 10 patients reporting mild cravings. By the 60th day, severe cravings were

completely eliminated, moderate cravings dropped to 20, and mild cravings increased to 40.

Acamprosate Craving Severity (N=60)	0th Day	30th Day	60th Day
Mild	0	10	40
Moderate	11	47	20
Severe	49	3	0

Table 2: Overall PACS score of the patients prescribed with Acamprosate

Table 3: shows a significant reduction in craving severity who are taking Baclofen by using PACS score. On the 0th day, cravings were predominantly severe (43 individuals), with a smaller portion experiencing moderate cravings (17 individuals), and none reporting mild cravings. By the 30th day, there

was a noticeable shift, with severe cravings drastically reducing to just 2 individuals, while moderate cravings increased to 49 and mild cravings emerged in 9 individuals. By the 60th day, the trend continued positively, with severe cravings completely eliminated, moderate cravings significantly reduced to 9 individuals, and mild cravings rising to 51

Baclofen Craving Severity (N=60)	0th Day	30th Day	60th Day
Mild	0	9	51
Moderate	17	49	9
Severe	43	2	0

Table 3: Overall PACS score of the patients prescribed with Baclofen

Fig 1 : Comparison between Acamprosate v/s Baclofen PACS

Fig 1 presents a comparative analysis of the severity of cravings by using PACS Score among individuals treated with Baclofen and Acamprosate over a period of 60 days, On Day 0, a significant number of individuals fall under the "Severe" category for both medications (43 for Baclofen and 49 for

Acamprosate). By the 30th day, severe cases have reduced (2 for Baclofen and 3 for Acamprosate), while moderate and mild cases have increased. By the 60th day, there are no severe cases, with most individuals showing mild cravings (51 for Baclofen and 40 for Acamprosate). Overall, the data suggests

that both Baclofen and Acamprosate are effective in reducing the severity of symptoms over time, with

Baclofen showing a slightly higher shift toward mild cases by the 60th day.

Table 4: Comparison of alcohol cravings as measured by PACS at 0th, 30th, 60th days between Acamprosate and baclofen treated patients.

Parameter	Acamprosate	Baclofen	p-value
0 th Day	22.73 ± 3.01	21.97 ± 2.96	0.4234
30 th Day	16.95 ± 2.92	16.22 ± 2.49	0.0167*
60 th Day	11.47 ± 3.46	10.65 ± 2.64	0.0045*

Table 4 Represents the Mean ± Standard Deviation (SD) values of PACS scores for Acamprosate and Baclofen at three different time points: On the **0th day**, there is **no significant difference** between **Acamprosate and Baclofen**. On the **30th and 60th**

days, there is a **significant difference** between the two treatments, as indicated by the **p-values** being less than 0.05. These results suggest that the effects of Acamprosate and Baclofen are similar initially (0th day) but diverge more over time, showing significant differences by the 30th and 60th days.

Figure 2: Comparison of PACS Scores Between Acamprosate and Baclofen Over time

Median values (red lines) show a downward trend, indicating a reduction in PACS scores over time.

DISCUSSION

The study was conducted on 120 patients diagnosed with Alcohol Use Disorder (AUD), who were equally divided into two treatment groups. One group was treated with Acamprosate (60 patients, 50%), and the other with Baclofen (60 patients, 50%). The objective was to assess and compare the effectiveness of these two medications in managing alcohol cravings and

dependence. The balanced distribution ensured that both treatment groups were equally represented, eliminating any bias in the results. The age distribution of patients showed that the highest proportion of AUD cases were in the 35-39 years age group (17%), followed by the 45-49 years group (15%). Other significant age groups included 40-44 years (12%), 50-54 years (12%), and 25-29 years (12%), indicating that AUD was most prevalent among middle-aged individuals. The lowest number of cases were observed in the youngest (20-24 years, 2%) and oldest (65-69 years, 1%) age groups. When

analysing treatment distribution within age groups, it was noted that Baclofen was more frequently administered to patients in the 35-39 years group (23.35%), whereas Acamprosate was more commonly prescribed to individuals in the 40-44 years group (16.67%). The study found that 90% of the patients were married, while only 10% were unmarried. The high percentage of married individuals suffering from AUD suggests that social, psychological, or familial stressors might contribute to excessive alcohol consumption. It also indicates that married individuals might be more likely to seek medical help compared to unmarried individuals. A significant portion of the patients, 80%, were illiterate, while only 20% were literate. This finding suggests a correlation between low educational levels and alcohol dependence, possibly due to a lack of awareness regarding the harmful effects of alcohol, fewer employment opportunities, and socioeconomic struggles leading to alcohol misuse. Regarding occupation, daily wage workers (26%) and drivers (22%) were the most affected groups, followed by factory workers (7%), shopkeepers (8%), and painters (6%). Other occupations such as carpenters, electricians, mechanics, and vegetable sellers also had smaller representations. The predominance of daily wage workers and drivers suggests that individuals engaged in physically demanding jobs with irregular working hours may be more vulnerable to alcohol use, possibly as a coping mechanism for work-related stress and exhaustion. The severity of alcohol dependence was assessed using the Severity of Alcohol Dependence Questionnaire (SAD-Q) during the first visit. The results showed that 49.2% of the patients had severe alcohol dependence, while 48.3% had moderate dependence, and only 2.5% had mild dependence.

Patients prescribed Acamprosate were assessed for craving severity using the Penn Alcohol Craving Scale (PACS). On the 0th day (before treatment), the majority of patients (81.66%) had severe cravings, while 18.34% had moderate cravings, and none had mild cravings. By the 30th day (first follow-up), a significant reduction in cravings was observed, with 78.34% of patients having moderate cravings, 16.66% having mild cravings, and only 5% still experiencing severe cravings. By the 60th day (second follow-up), cravings continued to decline, with 66.66% of patients experiencing mild cravings, 33.34% experiencing

moderate cravings, and no patients reporting severe cravings. The results indicate that Acamprosate was effective in gradually reducing alcohol cravings over time.

Similar to Acamprosate, patients treated with Baclofen were assessed for craving severity using PACS scores. On the 0th day, 71.67% of patients had severe cravings, while 28.33% had moderate cravings, and none had mild cravings. By the 30th day, the percentage of patients with severe cravings drastically dropped to 3.33%, while 81.67% had moderate cravings, and 15% had mild cravings. By the 60th day, the results further improved, with 85% of patients experiencing mild cravings, 15% experiencing moderate cravings, and no patients experiencing severe cravings. These findings suggest that Baclofen was slightly more effective in reducing cravings compared to Acamprosate, as it had a higher proportion of mild cases by the 60th day.

A direct comparison of craving severity between the two treatment groups revealed that both medications effectively reduced cravings over time. On Day 0, most patients in both groups had severe cravings (49 patients in Acamprosate, 43 in Baclofen). By Day 30, cravings were largely reduced to moderate levels in both groups, with Acamprosate showing slightly more moderate cases (47) compared to Baclofen (49). By Day 60, the shift towards mild cravings was more significant in the Baclofen group (85% mild cravings) than in the Acamprosate group (66.66% mild cravings). The comparison suggests that while both medications were effective, Baclofen demonstrated a slightly greater reduction in craving severity over time.

To analyze the effectiveness of both drugs statistically, PACS scores were compared at three different time points (0th, 30th, and 60th days). The mean PACS scores for Acamprosate and Baclofen showed a consistent decline over time, with Baclofen showing a slightly greater reduction. On the 0th day, Acamprosate had a mean PACS score of 22.73, while Baclofen had 21.97. By the 30th day, the scores reduced to 16.95 for Acamprosate and 16.22 for Baclofen. By the 60th day, the scores further dropped to 11.47 for Acamprosate and 10.65 for Baclofen. The p-values (<0.05) confirmed that these reductions were

statistically significant. This data indicates that both medications effectively reduced cravings, but Baclofen had a slightly superior effect in reducing PACS scores.

CONCLUSION

This study highlights the comparable efficacy of Acamprosate and Baclofen in managing Alcohol Use Disorder (AUD), with both medications effectively reducing alcohol cravings over a 60-day period. Baclofen demonstrated a marginal advantage, particularly in patients with moderate dependence and those experiencing higher initial craving scores. This study highlights the effectiveness of both Acamprosate and Baclofen in reducing alcohol cravings among AUD patients over 60 days. Given the statistically significant findings and individual responses, both medications should be considered viable options in clinical practice, with Baclofen showing a slight advantage in efficacy. Future studies should focus on long-term outcomes, side effect profiles, and individualized treatment responses across diverse patient populations.

LIMITATIONS

- The study focused exclusively on male patients, limiting the generalizability of results across genders.
- A longer follow-up period is necessary to assess long-term efficacy and relapse rates.
- Potential confounding factors such as comorbid psychiatric conditions were excluded, limiting real-world applicability.

Funding support

The authors declare that they have no funding support for this study.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Sharma A K, Rikhari P. et al. Role of Acamprosate and Baclofen as Anti-craving Agents in Alcohol Use Disorder: A 12-Week Prospective Study. *Cureus*. 2024;16(4):1-8.
2. Raje AL, Vaidya. et al. Safety Profile, Compliance, and Effectiveness of Baclofen and Acamprosate in Alcohol Use Disorder- A Retrospective Cohort Study. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*.2024;12(1): 2113-2121.
3. MuralidharanK,etal.Alcohol,DrugmisuseandOth eraddictions:Whattoknowandh owtogethelp.NIMHANSBangalore.2009.
4. Ominika Jarcuskova, Pallayova M et al. Clinical characteristics of adults with alcohol dependence syndrome comorbid with antisocial personality disorder: across-sectional study. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*. 2024 ;15(15) 306-311.
5. Ganesh Koppad, Deepak Suvarna, et al.Baclofen versus Acamprosate for Maintenance of Alcohol Abstinence in Patients with Cirrhosis of Liver: A Double Blinded Randomized Trial. *Surgery, Gastroenterology and Oncology* . 2024 ;28(4).
6. Ambekar A, Agrawal A, et al. on behalf of the group of investigators for the National Survey on Extent and Pattern of Substance Use in India (2019). *Magnitude of Substance Use in India*. New Delhi: Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment, Government of India.
7. Gadde P, Sai,et al. The Burden of Teenage Alcohol Consumption in Andhra Pradesh State, India—Epidemiology and Social Context. *Global Social Welfare*. 2022;9(4):253-259.
8. Kranzler HR. Overview of Alcohol Use Disorder. *American Journal of Psychiatry*. 2023;180(8):565–572.
9. Berger D. Medical Complications: Common Alcohol-Related Concerns National Institute on Alcohol Abuse and Alcoholism (NIAAA),2023.
10. Singh S, Wagh V.Marchiafava Bignami Disease: A Rare Neurological Complication of Long-Term Alcohol Abuse. 2033;14(10):1-9.
11. Winhusen T, Theobald J,et al. Medical complications associated with substance use disorders in patients with type 2 diabetes and hypertension: electronic health record findings. *Addiction*. 2019 ;114(8):1462–1470.
12. Jesse S, Bråthen G, et al.Alcohol withdrawal syndrome: mechanisms, manifestations, and

- management. *Acta Neurologica Scandinavica* . 2017;135(1):4-16.
13. Yang W, Singla R et al. Alcohol Use Disorder: Neurobiology and Therapeutics. *Biomedicines* . 2022;10(5):1-25.
 14. Dharavath RN, Pina-Leblanc C, et al. GABAergic signaling in alcohol use disorder and withdrawal: pathological involvement and therapeutic potential. *Frontiers in Neural Circuits* . 2023;vol:17.
 15. American Psychiatric Association. Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders (DSM-5-TR). American Psychiatric Association; 2024,5th edition.
 16. Pradeep RJ, Dhilip AM, et al. Do SADQ and AUDIT identify independent impacts of alcohol abuse - clinical and biochemical markers respectively?. *Indian J Psychiatry* 2015;57th edition:278-283.
 17. Foy A, March S, et al. Use of an Objective Clinical Scale in the Assessment and Management of Alcohol Withdrawal in a Large General Hospital. *Alcoholism: Clinical and Experimental Research*. 1988 ;12(3):360–364.
 18. Opozda-Suder S, Karteczka-Świątek K, et al. Psychometric properties and longitudinal measurement invariance of the drug craving scale: Modification of the Polish version of the Penn Alcohol Craving Scale (PACS). 2021 ;16(9):1-14.
 19. Ray LA, Meredith LR, et al. Combined Pharmacotherapy and Cognitive Behavioral Therapy for Adults With Alcohol or Substance Use Disorders. 2020 , 19;3(6):1-15.
 20. Hendershot CS, Witkiewitz K, et al. Relapse prevention for addictive behaviors. *Substance Abuse Treat Prev Policy*. 2011;6(17):1-17 .
 21. Barbara S. McCrady ,Julianne C. Flanagan, The Role of The family in alcohol Use Disorder Recovery for adults, *Alcohol Res*. 2021;41(1)
 22. Abhijeet Singh, & Arif Ali. . Group Therapy in Alcohol Dependence: A Hospital-Based Study. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*,2022; 10(2).
 23. Vannier, Augustin G.L. et al. Psychotherapy for Alcohol Use Disorder Is Associated With Reduced Risk of Incident Alcohol-Associated Liver Disease *Clinical Gastroenterology and Hepatology*, 21(6), 1571 - 1580.
 24. Holt SR, Tobin DG. Pharmacotherapy for Alcohol Use Disorder. *Medical Clinics of North America*. 2018 Jul;102(4):653–666.
 25. Burnette EM, Nieto SJ, et al. Novel Agents for the Pharmacological Treatment of Alcohol Use Disorder. *Drugs*. 2022 ;82(3):251–74.
 26. Dr. Robert M. Swift, MD, et al. Pharmacotherapy for Alcohol Use Disorder: Current and Emerging Therapies, *Harv Rev Psychiatry*. 2015 ; 23(2): 122–133.
 27. Modesto-Lowe V, Barron GC, et al. Gabapentin for alcohol use disorder: A good option, or cause for concern? *Cleveland Clinic Journal of Medicine* . 2019 ;86(12);1-24.
 28. Mayfield RD, Harris RA, et al. Genetic factors influencing alcohol dependence. *British Journal of Pharmacology [Internet]*. 2009;154(2):275–287.
 29. Tyler RE, Leggio L. Biological basis of addiction and alcohol use disorder. *Clinical Liver Disease* . 2024;23(1):1-4.
 30. Isabel margherita Berri AZ *frontiers in psychiatry*. Psychological dimensions in alcohol use disorder: comparing active drinkers and abstinent patients . 2024.
 31. .Chartier KG, Karriker-Jaffe KJ,et al. Review: Environmental influences on alcohol use: Informing research on the joint effects of genes and the environment in diverse U.S. populations. *The American Journal on Addictions [Internet]*. 2018 Jan 2;26(5):446–460.
 32. .Anthenelli RM, Brady KT, Grandison L, Roach D. Co-Occurring Alcohol Use Disorder and Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder. *Alcohol research : current reviews [Internet]*. 2018;39(2):111–2.
 33. Kumar A, Sharma A et al. A comparative study on the safety and efficacy of naltrexone versus baclofen versus acamprosate in the management of alcohol dependence. *Indian Journal of Psychiatry*.2020; 62(6): 650-658.
 34. Sudhir P , Devesh G et al. Adverse drug reactions of baclofen, naltrexone, and acamprosate in patients having alcohol dependence: a cross-sectional pharmacovigilance study. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*.2024;17(4): 111-114.
 35. Tolomeo.S, Baldacchino.A. Adherence to Prescribed Acamprosate in Alcohol Dependence and 1-Year Morbidities and Mortality: Utilizing a

- Data Linkage Methodology. Journal of Clinical Medicine.2021;10(10):1-10
36. Ambekar A, Agrawal A et al. on behalf of the group of investigators for the National Survey on Extent and Pattern of Substance Use in India (2019). Magnitude of Substance Use in India. New Delhi: Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment, Government of India.
37. Joseph T Dipiro, et al. PHARMACOTHERAPY A pathophysiological approach 8th edition :1193-1198.
38. Renaud de beaurepaire and Philippe Jaury et al. "baclofen in the treatment of alcohol use disorder: tailored doses matter" 2024 Jan 23;59(2):1-10
39. Soundarya Soundararajan, Pratima Murthy et al., " High craving is associated with fewer abstinent days and lesser time to relapse during treatment in severe alcohol use disorder" Indian Journal of Psychiatry March 2023;65(3):319-326
40. Ratan kharb, Lokesh S et al., conducted a study on "Relationship between craving and early relapse in alcohol dependence: A short term follow up study". Indian J Psychol Med.2018 Jul-Aug;40(4):315-321.

HOW TO CITE: R.V.S.S. Latha Sri, A. Chandra Sekhar, R. Srinivas, S. Divya, T. Vamsi, J.N. Suresh Kumar, A Prospective Observational Study On Comparing The Efficacy Of Acamprosate And Baclofen In The Treatment Of Alcohol Use Disorder In A Tertiary Care Hospital, J. Pharm. Sci., 2026, 2 (5), 227-235. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20044705>

